

Ecological context

Please, reply below to each of the following 18 questions, providing as little information as possible, but include relevant details. Remember that we (WP2) are not familiar with your Replication Site and your restoration plan. You don't have to worry about the narrative. Bullet points are ok.

As always, if you have any doubts please reach out!

1. Describe the intervention area, is it inside a Marine Protected Area?
2. What are the causes of decline?
3. Who has tenure / ownership / management responsibility of the marine space?
4. Who has tenure / ownership of the adjacent land?
5. Who currently has marine resource access rights within the area of intervention?
6. Will the intervention result in restrictions or changes to access and resource use?
7. What other activities (e.g., recreational) are currently conducted within the area of intervention?
8. Will the intervention result in restrictions or changes to these activities?
9. Describe the intervention – what is being restored?
10. What is the ecological baseline that is being used to evaluate the need for restoration?
11. What was the cause of the decline in the status of the targeted biodiversity?
12. Have the causes of this decline been stopped or otherwise mitigated?
13. How is the intervention being conducted?
14. Describe the aspects of the intervention that involve technical solutions
15. Describe the aspects of the intervention that involve nature-based solutions
16. How will the restoration decrease climate vulnerability?
17. Have there been any conflicts over resource use, conservation, or restoration at this site before?
18. Are any of the methods that you plan to use controversial? In what way/why? If so, which stakeholders have been involved?